

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry

Title of the course: ***Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry I*** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours: **Theory 3 hours Laboratory 1 hour**

Reference text: ***Wilson and Gisvold Textbook of Organic medicinal and Pharmaceutical chemistry, Delgado JN, Remers WA, (Eds); . Latest edition.***

Objectives

To enable understanding mechanisms of drug action at molecular : . level and the role of medicinal chemistry in the discovery and development of synthetic -therapeutic agents. It also enables students to understand the concept of structure activity relationship and its application in design and synthesis of new compounds or derivative.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Drug distribution	4
2	Acid- base properties.	3
3	Statistical prediction of pharmacological activity.	3
4	QSAR models.	2
5	Molecular modeling (Computer aided drug design).	1
6	Drug receptor interaction: force involved.	1
7	Steric features of drugs.	2
8	Optical isomerism and biological activity.	1
9	Calculated conformation.	1
10	Three- dimensional quantitative structure activity relationships and databases	1
11	Isosterism.	1
12	Drug-receptor interaction and subsequent events.	1
13	General pathways of drug metabolism: Sites of drug biotransformation;Role of cytochrome P450 mono-oxygenases in oxidative biotransformation; Oxidative reactions; Reductive reactions; Hydrolytic reactions; Phase II reactions.	22
14	Factors affecting drug metabolism	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry

Title of the course: ***Practical Organic Pharmaceutical Chemistry I***

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours: **1**

Reference text: ***Lab Handbook for Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry***

Adopted by the Department

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Preparation and standardization of 0.1N KMnO ₄ (known sample).	2
2	Preparation and standardization of 0.1N KMnO ₄ (quiz and unknown).	2
3	Assay of hydrogen peroxide solution (known sample).	2
4	Assay of hydrogen peroxide solution (quiz and unknown sample).	2
5	Assay of ferrous sulfate (known sample).	2
6	Assay of ferrous sulfate (unknown sample).	2
7	Preparation and standardization of 0.1Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄ solution (known sample).	2
8	Preparation and standardization of 0.1Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄ solution (quiz and unknown sample).	2
9	Assay of copper sulfate (known sample).	2
10	Assay of copper sulfate (unknown sample).	2
11	Assay of Chlorinated Lime (known sample).	2
12	Assay of Chlorinated Lime (quiz and unknown).	2
13	Preparation and assay of Lugol's Solution (known sample).	2
14	Preparation and assay of Lugol's Solution (quiz and unknown).	2
15	Assay of Alum (unknown sample)	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: ***Biochemistry II*** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week : **Theory 3 Laboratory 1**

Reference text: Harper' s Illustrated Biochemistry. Latest edition.

Objectives

: To provide a condensed curriculum of strong basic biochemistry and molecular biology. At the end of the semester the students should be able to understand all metabolic processes occurring in the living cell.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Bioenergetics.	2
2	Biologic oxidation	2
3	The respiratory chain and oxidative phosphorylation	2
4	Over view of metabolism	2
5	Citric acid Cycle	2
6	Glycolysis.	2
7	Metabolism of glycogen	4
8	Gluconeogenesis.	3
9	Pentose phosphate pathway and other pathways of hexose metabolism	3
10	Biosynthesis of fatty acids.	3
11	Oxidation of fatty acids.	2
12	Metabolism of acylglycerol and sphingolipids.	2
13	Lipid transport and storage.	2
14	Cholesterol synthesis, transport, and excretion.	2
15	Biosynthesis of the Nutritionally Nonessential Amino Acids.	3
16	Catabolism of Proteins & of Amino Acid Nitrogen	3
17	Catabolism of the Carbon Skeletons of Amino Acids.	2
18	Conversion of Amino Acids to Specialized Products.	2
19	Porphyrins & Bile Pigments	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences

Title of the course: Biochemistry II Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week : Laboratory 1

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University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Professional Pharmacy Practice Skills**

Level: **3rd Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theoretical 1 hour+ 1 hr. lab.**

Reference:

- 1-Karen J. Tietze. Clinical skills for pharmacists A Patient-Focused Approach. Latest edition.
- 2-Ruth E. Nemire, Karen L. Kier. pharmacystudent survival guide. Latest edition.
- 3-Manual prepared by the Clinical Pharmacy Department.

Objective:

This course teaches skills pharmacists can use to gather information for monitoring effectiveness of drug therapy besides identifying and resolving drug therapy problems.

Additionally students will have a chance to visit the hospital to implement the skills and observing different diagnostic procedures, medical supplies, and the hospital pharmacy organization.

The patient care skills and tasks taught in this course will prepare students to enter into hospitals during the first Introductory hospital Pharmacy Practice Experience.

No	Title	hours
1	Part one: laboratory exercises (practical techniques in small groups) to cover: 1- Patient interview and the history taking :Collect necessary subjective and objective data to understand relevant medical/medication history and clinical status of the patient.	16

	<p>2- Performing a basic vital sign assessment (e.g. blood pressure, pulse, temperature, respirations, height, weight) and interpret data for a simulated patient.</p> <p>3. Performing simple physical examination (Inspection, Palpation, Percussion, and Auscultation Techniques).</p> <p>3-Laboratory Tests, Diagnostic Procedures and medical supplies:</p> <p>A-Laboratory Tests(Interpretation of ClinicalLaboratory Data)</p> <p>B-Diagnostic Procedures: clinical utility of different diagnostic procedures including (Angiography, Computed tomography (CT scan), Doppler Echography, Echocardiography, Endoscopy, Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Ultrasonography, Cardiac Catheterization, ECG, Exercise ECG echocardiography, Exercise echocardiography, dialysis, plasmapheresis, and others).</p> <p>C- Common Medical supplies (Different types of cannulas, i.v. giving sets, nebulizer, sucker, ambu bag, catheter, colostomy bag, infusion pump,and others)</p> <p>4-Identification and classification of Drug related Problems</p> <p>5- Developing and implementing action plan. Clinical Decision Making.</p> <p>6-Patienteducation/Counseling about medications and health wellness</p> <p>7-Monitoring efficacy and adverse effects of drug therapy</p> <p>A. Determine an overall therapeutic goal when a particular problem is to be treated; establish a therapeutic goal for each form of therapy</p> <p>B. List monitoring parameters that will determine whether goals are being met</p> <p>C. Identify the common and/or significant adverse reactions for each drug selected, and identify the parameters necessary to monitor for drug toxicity</p> <p>8-Automation in pharmacy practice</p> <p>9-Providing Drug Information</p>	
2	Part two: clinical rotations	

	Implementing the skills provided in the first part in real practice supervised by the instructors Additionally students will have a chance to observe different diagnostic procedures , Medical devices , and the hospital pharmacy organization .	8
3	Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs)	6

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Pharmacoepidemiology**

Level: **3rd Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 1 hours.**

Reference:

- 1- Brenda Waning, Michael Montagne. Pharmacoepidemiology: Principles and Practice. Latest edition.
- 2- Yi Yang, Donna West-Strum. Understanding Pharmacoepidemiology. Latest edition.

Objective:

Understanding pharmacoepidemiology and its importance in pharmacy practice, principles of epidemiology applied to the study of medication use, medication safety pharmacovigilance, post-marketing surveillance, and applications in pharmacy practice.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to health/Pharmacoeconomics	1
2	Basic principles and terminology in Pharmacoeconomics , Determination of cost and outcomes	2
3	Measuring patient outcomes for use in economic evaluations	2
4	Type of pharmacoeconomics evaluations [Cost –minimization analysis (CMA), Cost effectiveness analysis (CEA), Cost utility analysis (CUA), Cost benefit analysis (CBA), Budget Impact analysis (BIA)]	6
5	Decision analysis in economic evaluations, The use of Pharmacoeconomic in policy making and informing health decision.	2
6	Preview of published Pharmacoeconomic researchs	2
7	Introduction to pharmacoepidemiology	2

8	Principles of Epidemiology Applied to the Study of Medication Use	2
9	Medical Surveillance and Outbreaks of Disease	2
10	Medication Safety and Pharmacovigilance	2
11	Post-Marketing Surveillance	2
12	Medication Utilization Patterns	2
13	Risk Assessment	1

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmaceutics

Title of the course: ***Pharmaceutical Technology II*** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week: **Theory 3 Laboratory 1**

Reference text: ***Pharmaceutical Dosage forms and Drug Delivery Systems By Haward A. Ansel; latest edition.*** and ***Sprowel's American Pharmacy.***

Objectives: To teach theoretical bases for the technology of preparing different dosage forms with respect to their raw materials, compositions, methods of preparation, stability, storage and uses; in addition to define and characterize the possible incompatibilities that may occur in dosage forms.

No.	Lecture title	hours
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1	Emulsions; purpose of emulsification; methods of emulsification; emulsifying agents; HLB system; stability of emulsions.	10
2	Lotions; liniments and collodions.	5
3	Suppositories.	6
4	Powdered dosage forms.	10
5	Semisolid dosage forms.	10
6	Incompatibilities in pharmaceutical dosage forms.	4

University of Baghdad
College of Pharmacy Department
of Pharmaceutics

Title of the course: ***Practical Pharmaceutical Technology II***

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week : 1

Reference text: ***Lab Manual for Practical pharmaceutical Technology Adopted by the Department.***

Objectives: To teach theoretical bases for the technology of preparing different dosage forms with respect to their raw materials, compositions, methods of preparation, stability, storage and uses; in addition to define and characterize the possible incompatibilities that may occur in dosage forms.

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Emulsions: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	6
2	Suppositories: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	6
3	Powders: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	6
4	Capsules: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	6
5	Semisolid dosage forms: Preparation techniques and quality evaluation.	6

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Community pharmacy**

Level: **3rd Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hours, Laboratory 1**

Reference Text:

1-Alison Blenkinsopp, Paul Paxton(eds), Symptoms in the Pharmacy. A Guide to the Management of Common Illness. Latest edition.

2- Community Pharmacy. Symptoms, Diagnosis and Treatment. By Paul Rutter. Latest edition.

3- American pharmacists association. Handbook of Non-prescription drugs: An Interactive Approach to Self-Care. Latest edition.

Objective:

The course provides students with basic knowledge and skills in community pharmacy in terms of management and practice.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to community pharmacy	1
2	Respiratory Problems (Colds and flu, Cough, Sore throat, Allergic rhinitis (hay fever)	3
3	Gastrointestinal Tract Problems (Mouth ulcers, Heartburn, Indigestion, Constipation, Diarrhoea, Irritable bowel syndrome, Haemorrhoids, Intestinal Gas, Ostomy Care and Supplies)	6
4	Skin Conditions (Eczema/dermatitis, Acne, Fungal skin infections, Cold sores, Warts and verrucae, Scabies, Dandruff, Psoriasis, Hair loss (androgenetic alopecia), Sun exposure and melanoma risk, Corns and calluses, Minor Burns, Sunburn, and Wounds, Skin Hyperpigmentation and Photoaging, Insect Bites and Stings).	8
5	Women's Health (Cystitis, Dysmenorrhoea, Menorrhagia, Vaginal thrush, Emergency hormonal contraception, Premenstrual syndrome)	2

6	Childhood Conditions (Illnesses affecting infants and children up to 16 years, Colic, Teething, Napkin rash, Head lice, Threadworms (pinworms), Oral thrush)	2
7	Central nervous system (Headache, Insomnia, Motion sickness and its prevention)	2
8	Musculoskeletal conditions (Acute low back pain, Activity-related/sports-related soft tissue injuries)	1
9	Men's Health (Benign prostatic hyperplasia)	1
10	Eye Problems (Red eye , Eyelid disorders , Dry eye, Foreign Substances in the Eye, Minor Eye Irritation, Chemical Burn, Prevention of Contact Lens-Related Disorders)	3
11	Ear Problems (Ear wax impaction , Water Clogged Ears, Otitis externa)	1
12	Oral care (Caries, Tooth Hypersensitivity , Gingivitis, Halitosis, Hygiene-Related Denture Problems, Xerostomia)	2
13	Tobacco Cessation	1
14	Home Testing and Monitoring Devices	2
15	Overweight and Obesity	2
16	Infant Nutrition and Special Nutritional Needs of Children	2
17	Sports Nutrition and Performance Enhancing Nutrients	2
18	Ostomy Care and Supplies, Adult Urinary Incontinence and Supplies	1
19	An update in reclassification of OTC drugs	1
20	Medication adherence and errors	2

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: practical Community Pharmacy

Level: **3rd Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours /week : Practical 1 hours

Reference:

Manual prepared by the Clinical Pharmacy Department.

No	Lecture title	hours
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1	Communication with patients.	2
2	Respiratory system in practice (part I): Cough.	2
3	Respiratory system in practice (part II): Common cold.	2
4	G.I.T system in practice (part I): Constipation.	2
5	G.I.T system in practice (part II): Diarrhea and IBS.	2
6	GIT system in practice (part III): GERD& indigestion.	2
7	Collective practice.	2
8	Skin conditions in practice (part I): Hair loss; cold sore and athlete's foot.	2
9	Skin conditions in practice (part II): Dandruff, Eczema and mouth ulcer.	2
10	Skin conditions in practice (part III): warts and scabies.	2
11	Pediatrics in practice: Oral thrush; colic; pinworm and napkin rash.	2
12	Minor eye and ear disorders in practice.	2
13	CNS system: Insomnia, motion sickness, and nicotine replacement therapy (NRT).	2
14	Collective practice.	2
15	Collective practice.	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology

Title of the course: **Pharmacology II** Course number:

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week: **Theory 3 Laboratory 1**

Reference text: **Lipincott Pharmacology**. Latest edition.

Objectives

: To introduce the pharmacy students to the general pharmacology of the central nervous system and to the various drug groups used in the treatment of CNS diseases or drugs altering its function. The students will be introduced to the various drugs used in the management of cardiovascular diseases. Moreover, the course will cover the drugs affecting the gastrointestinal and respiratory systems

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	The autonomic nervous system (ANS).	2
2	Cholinergic system.	4

3	Adrenergic system.	5
4	Diuretics.	2
5	Antihypertensive drugs.	4
6	The treatment of heart failure (HF).	3
7	Antianginal Drugs.	2
8	Antiarrhythmic drugs.	2
9	Drugs affecting the blood.	4
10	Anti-hyperlipidemia drugs.	2
11	Insulin and oral hypoglycemic drugs.	3
12	Drugs for disorders of the respiratory system.	3
13	Gastrointestinal and antiemetic drugs.	3
14	Drugs for urologic disorders	2
15	Drugs for obesity	2
16	Drugs for dermatologic disorders	2
17	The autonomic nervous system (ANS).	2

University of Baghdad

**College of Pharmacy Department
of Pharmacology and Toxicology**

Title of the course: ***Practical Pharmacology II***

Level: 3rd Class, 2nd Semester

Credit hours/week: **1 hr.**

Reference text: ***Lab Manual for Practical Pharmacology Adopted by the
Department***

Objectives: To teach students the practice of application of Pharmacological principles in animal, and to understand the bases for evaluation of the pharmacological activity of drugs and chemicals in

No.	Lecture title	hours
1	Routs of drug administration	4
2	Onset and duration of drugs (Barbiturates)	2
3	Absorption and excretion of drugs	2
4	Effect of parasympathomimetics on gland secretions	2
5	Drugs and human eye.	4
6	The effects of drugs on IOP rabbits	2
7	Evaluation of opioid analgesics	2
8	Evaluation of NSAIDS	4
9	Evaluation of anti-parkinsonian drugs	2
10	Evaluation of anti- convulsant drugs	2
11	The effects of drugs and their antagonists on isolated rats ileum	2
12	The effects of drugs and their antagonists on isolated rabbits ileum	2

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Communication skills**

Level: **3rd Class, 1st Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hours.**

Reference Text:

1-Robert S. Beardsley, (ed.); Communication Skills in Pharmacy Practice. Latest edition.

2-Bruce A. Berger. Communication Skills for Pharmacists: Building Relationships, Improving Patient Care. Latest edition.

Objective:

This course covers theories in communication and patient counseling, applications and communication techniques.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Patient-Centered Communication in Pharmacy Practice	2
2	Principles and Elements of Interpersonal Communication	2

3	Nonverbal type of communication.	2
4	Barriers to communication.	2
5	Listening and empathic responding during communication.	2
6	Assertiveness.	2
7	Interviewing and assessment.	2
8	Helping patients to manage therapeutic regimens.	2
9	Patient counseling; counseling check list; point-by-point discussion; counseling scenario.	2
10	Medication safety and communication skills.	2
11	Strategies to meet specific needs.	2
12	Communicating with children and elderly about medications.	2
13	Communication skills and inter-professional collaboration.	2
14	Electronic communication in healthcare.	2
15	Ethical behavior when communicating with patients	2

Summer training, I (Community pharmacy practice)